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An Incidence Of Suspected Adverse Drug Reaction: A Single Case Study

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Abstract

Ayurvedaa a traditional system of medicine practiced in the Indian subcontinent is usually considered to be devoid of adverse reactions. In this case study we are reporting an adverse reaction occurred due to overdose of *Shwasakuthar rasa*. A 34 year old man with *Tamak Shwas* consumed *Ayurveda* rasa for almost a year in a dosage of 2 tab BDs along with water as *Anupana*. Later there developed blackish discolouration of skin all over the body. Misconception about full safety of *Ayurveda*ic medicine leads many patients to consume them for years without any monitoring/prescription from *vaidya*. Inorganic mercury as observed leads to corrosive effect of skin, eyes, GIT and nephrotoxicity and also hyper/hypo pigmentation all over the body. This makes *vaidya* to think of multiple and life threatening diseases like Addison's disease, Albinism, primary biliary cholangitis, primary biliary cirrhosis when detailed *Nidan* analysis is not done. Hyperpigmentation can also be caused by heavy metals poisoning like mercury, silver, gold etc which are considered as Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs). This happens commonly due to injudicious intake of medicines prepared out of these heavy metals or even due to wrong method of preparation. So a stringent monitoring to avoid such consequences is a need of an hour. Further in full paper we will be discussing regarding a case developed due to adverse drug reaction.

Keywords : *Parada*(Mercury), ADR, *Shwasakuthar rasa*.

Introduction-

A 34 years old man was brought by his relative to the OPD. Clinical examination revealed blackish discolouration of all over body, mild itching occasionally. History was taken in brief the probable cause finding like a taking of *Ayurveda rasa* since last 6 month so there is chances of the ADR of *Shwasakuthara rasa*. Mode of action of *Ayurveda Rasa Shwasakuthara Rasa* acts on *Shwasa Roga* due to the action of its ingredients which directly act on *pranavaha Srotas*. Its most of the ingredients are *Vatakaphashamaka* and mainly *Kapha- Nihsaraka*

with *Laghu, Ruksha* and *Ushna Guna*, means mainly acts on *Agnimandhya* and breaks the *Kapha Dosha Pradhan Samprapti*. It is contraindicated in pleural effusion, cardiac involvement and *Paittik Kasa*. Its role is limited as it increases the *Ushna guna* in many patients which was also observed in this study. Black pepper is a major constituent, which stimulate mucous membrane of the respiratory system. It helps in mucous drainage and imparts strength to alveolar mucous membrane. *Aconitum ferox* is antispasmodic in nature, hot and stimulant for mucous membrane. *Shunthi* and *Pippali* release the sputum.

Realgar absorbs excessive secretion from the alveoli. Purified borax is antispasmodic and removes *kapha*.

Materials & Methods-

Composition of *Shwas Kuthar Rasa*

SR. NO	Ingredients	Latin name/English Name	Part used	Quantity
1	<i>Shuddha Parada</i>	Mercury	-	1 tanka
2	<i>Shuddha Gandhak</i>	Sulphur		1 tanka
3	<i>Shuddha Vatsanabha</i>	Aconitum Ferox	Rhizome	1 tanka
4	<i>Tankana Bhasma</i>	Borex		1 tanka
5	<i>Manahashila</i>	Red Arsenic		1 tanka
6	<i>Sunthi</i>	Zingiber officinale	Rhizome	
7	<i>Maricha</i>	Piper Longum	Fruit	8 tanka
8	<i>Pippali</i>	Piper Longum	Fruit root	

Dosage - 2 Rati(125mg-250mg)

Anupana-Madhu

1. *Shuddha Parada Parada* is one of the pure and auspicious metal. it has not only spiritual and religious significance, but has extensive healing properties also. When *Parada*, which is impure is purified and consecrated by various processes, it become solid and known as *Shuddha Parada*. It is one of the important core ingredients in *Rasa ausadhies*. *Rasapanchak of Parada Rasa- shadarasa Guna – snigdha, sara, Virya – Ushna Vipak – Madhura*, Effect of *Dosha-Tridoshaghna*. Important properties of *parada* are described as-(*Tridoshaghna*). (*Rasayana*). (*Yogavahi*). (*Mahavrishya*). (*Sadadrishitibala Parada*). ACTION Mercury binds with sulfhydryl groups resulting in enzyme inhibition and pathological alteration of cellular membranes Inorganic mercury salts are corrosive to the skin, eyes, and GIT, and nephrotoxic.

2. *Shuddha Gandhak* Rasapanchak Rasa (taste)-Katu, Tikta, Kashaya. (property)-Sara Veerya(Potency)- UshnaVipaka-Madhura.

3. *Shuddha vatsanabha* Rasapanchak Rasa Madhura Guna-Ruksha, Teekshna, Laghu, Vyavayi, Vikasi Veerya-Ushna Vipaka-Madhura

4. *Manahashila* Rasapanchak Rasa(taste)- Katu, Tikta. Guna(property)-Snigdha, Guru, Sara. Veerya-Ushna

5. *Shuddha Tankan* - Rasapanchak Rasa-Madhura Guna-Ruksha, Teekshna, Laghu, Vyavayi, Vikasi Veerya-Ushna Vipaka-Madhura

6. *Sunthi*- Rasa Panchak Rasa(taste)-Katu Guna (Property)- Laghu, Snigdha, Teekshna. Veerya (potency)-Anuashna. Vipaka-Madhura

7. *Maricha*- Rasapanchak Rasa(taste)-Katu Guna (property)- Laghu, Teekshna Veerya (Potency)-Ushna Vipaka-Katu

8. *Pippali*- Rasapanchak Rasa (taste)- Katu Guna (Property)- Laghu, Snigdha, Teekshna. Veerya a (potency)-Anushna. Vipaka - Madhura

9. Discussion & Conclusion-

In this case, patient of *Tamak Shwas* treated in past history. So the Physician advised to the patient consume *Shwaskuthar rasa* 2 tab BDs in Dose for a 1 month with *Ardraka swara as anupana*. But patient consumed 2 BD for a year without any consultation by the physician or even without any monitoring. Gradually patient notice mild blackish discoloration of the skin. After his family members reported regarding the same to him. Initially he neglected the same but after few months the condition worsened and blackish pigmentation became extensive throughout the body. Intake of *Shwaskuthar rasa* for a long time which has Inorganic mercury as observed leads to corrosive effect of skin, eyes, GIT and nephrotoxicity and also hyper/hypo pigmentation all over the body. This makes physician to think of multiple and life threatening diseases like Addison's disease, Albinism, Primary biliary cholangitis, Primary biliary cirrhosis when detailed Nidan analysis is not done. Hyperpigmentation also caused by heavy metals like mercury, silver, gold which can be poisonous. Also leads by certain NSAIDs,

barbiturates. So after that we approached to lab investigations like RFT S.cortisol but the Investigative values were normal. So we excluded the Addison's disease. There is no specific finding which indicates primary biliary cholangitis & primary biliary cirrhosis and patient had no history of taking NSAIDs since last 1 year. so these diagnosis were also excluded. So after excluding above said disease like Addison's disease, Albinism, Primary biliary cholangitis, Primary biliary cirrhosis. When thorough and detailed *nidan* analysis was done we notice injudicious, unprescribed intake of *shwasakuthara rasa* for almost a 1 year. Further when literature review also supported to same and also different articles were referred we came to conclusion that the blackish pigmentation was developed might be due to adverse reaction of *shwasakuthar rasa*. So it becomes primary responsibility of any practitioner to analyze proper history followed by *Nidana*. Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) significantly cause morbidity and mortality worldwide. As a result, proper Adverse Drug Reactions monitoring is required. Every ayurveda practitioner's responsibility is to detect ADR.

The study revealed that patient consuming medicine for long time without any guidance of physician. And it lead to adverse drug reaction of *shwaskuthar rasa* one of the ingredient is *parada* (Mercury). So it is heavy metal and poisons so consuming parad for long time can leads mercury poisoning and leads blackish discoloration of all over body. Before that lots of drugs had ADRs issue but this is the one of the example of ADR. So Always consume medicine under the guidance of physician, he knows the proper mechanism of drug their dose duration and side effects. The Adverse drug reactions are depends on timing, the pattern of illness, the results of investigations, and rechallenge. So for Prevention of adverse effects to drugs Adverse drug effects can be minimized but not altogether eliminated by observing the following practices. 1) Avoid all inappropriate use of drugs in the context of patient's clinical condition. 2) Use appropriate dose,

route and frequency of drug administration based on patient's specific variables. 3) Rule out possibility of drug interactions when more than one drug is prescribed. 4) Adopt correct drug administration technique 5) Carry out appropriate laboratory monitoring.

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